

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR 1156	ELEVATION Min: 63.3272 Max: 63.5696	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1156 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Anthropropic	
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 664-665	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:	
DEFINITION rubble layer				Covered by <input type="checkbox"/> SU: 1616	Fills <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1209	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction		FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition				
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are				SOIL/MATRIX		
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery m <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles r <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) rubble <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		
				clay 30% silt 70% sand ___% <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive		
				Compaction		Color
				<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft		<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original		<input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		
Southern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original		<input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		
Western Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original		<input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		
Eastern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original		<input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE						
Is equal to:				Is bound to (only for masonry):		
Is abutted by:				Abuts: 1164, 1190		
Is covered by: 1016				Covers:		
Is cut by: 1132				Cuts:		
Is filled by:				Fills: 1209		
OBSERVATIONS excavated with trowels, pick-axe, and shovel.						
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: nor th west Shape: rectangular shape cut by grave (1132) on northern edge						
For layers complete this section:						
Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions):						
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope) tufo rubble throughout layers						
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):						
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commigled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)						
For cuts complete this section:				Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):		
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight						
Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping						
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular						
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded						
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded						
Observations:						

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

residual rubble layer with pottery and bone
of medium frequency; covers crushed tufo floor

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets): 2

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by EWB

on 19.07.2010

Revised by CMM

on 20.07.2010

PDFd by JJM

on 23.07.2010

Entered by

on